

Collaborative Research: GEO OSE TRACK 2: Project Pythia and Pangeo: Building an inclusive geoscience community through accessible, reusable, and reproducible workflows

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Abstract

This project builds upon the demonstrable success of two community-driven open geoscience efforts: Pangeo and Project Pythia. Pangeo has advanced transformative platforms and paradigms for “Big Data” geoscience in the cloud; Pythia has built open, interactive learning resources for Python-based geoscience workflows built on public cloud datasets that “just work” for users. The central goal of this project is to reduce barriers to scientific progress by building community around shared scientific workflow knowledge, using the Pythia Cookbook format. “Cookbooks” imply collections of recipes for transforming raw ingredients (publicly available data) into scientifically useful results. Cookbooks are based on Jupyter notebooks but explicitly tied to reproducible computational environments and supported by a rich infrastructure enabling collaborative authoring and automated health-checking – essential tools in the struggle against the widespread problem of notebook obsolescence. Open-access, cloud-based Cookbooks are a democratizing force for science. By growing the collection of Pythia Cookbooks while growing the community of users, contributors, and maintainers, this project will grow the capacity of current and future geoscientists to practice open science within the rapidly evolving open science ecosystem.

Project Pythia exists to house, share, and accelerate the development of high-quality learning resources for Python-based computing in the geosciences. This project will advance geoscience research and education by developing, documenting, and propagating best practices for highly scalable reproducible data analysis in the cloud using the open-source ecosystem. The Pythia team will develop science-driven exemplar Cookbooks demonstrating highly scalable versions of common analysis workflows on high-value datasets across numerous geoscience domains, with content chosen to accelerate community awareness and participation. Content will span disciplines including Atmospheric Science, Physical Oceanography, Hydrology, Glaciology, Climate Science, and applications of Machine Learning. Infrastructure will be deployed for performant data-proximate Cookbook authoring, testing, and use, on both commercial and NSF-funded cloud platforms. Both the Cookbook collection and the community of user-contributors will broaden and grow through annual workshops, outreach, and classroom use, with recruitment specifically targeting under-served communities. Priorities will be guided by an independent steering board; sustainability will be achieved by nurturing a vibrant, inclusive community backed by automation that lowers barriers to participation.

PROJECT SUMMARY

Overview:

This project builds upon the demonstrable success of two community-driven open geoscience efforts: Pangeo and Project Pythia. Pangeo has advanced transformative platforms and paradigms for “Big Data” geoscience in the cloud; Pythia has reduced access barriers to this knowledge through open, interactive learning resources for Python-based geoscience workflows built on public cloud datasets that “just work” for users. The Pythia Cookbook is a format to house crowd-sourced collections of advanced, domain-specific tutorials and exemplar workflows. Cookbooks are based on Jupyter notebooks but explicitly tied to reproducible computational environments and supported by a rich infrastructure enabling collaborative authoring and automated health-checking. The central goal of this project is to reduce barriers to scientific progress by building community around shared scientific workflow knowledge using Cookbooks. We will develop science-driven exemplar Cookbooks demonstrating highly scalable versions of common analysis workflows on high-value datasets across numerous geoscience domains, with content chosen to accelerate community awareness and participation. Infrastructure will be deployed for performant data-proximate Cookbook authoring, testing, and use, on both commercial and NSF-funded cloud platforms. We will grow the collection of accessible, reusable, and reproducible Cookbooks in our gallery, as well as broadening the community of user-contributors, through annual workshops, outreach, and classroom use. Priorities will be guided by an independent steering board; sustainability will be achieved by nurturing a vibrant, inclusive community backed by automation that lowers barriers to participation.

CloudAccess

Intellectual Merit:

Project Pythia exists to house and share high-quality learning resources for Python-based computing in the geosciences. This project will advance geoscience research and education by developing, documenting, and propagating best practices for highly scalable reproducible data analysis in the cloud using the open source ecosystem. Content will span disciplines including Atmospheric Science, Physical Oceanography, Hydrology, Glaciology, Climate Science, and applications of Machine Learning. Project Pythia is first and foremost a learning resource.

Broader Impacts:

Cookbooks are a democratizing force for science. They are open access and backed by an interactive execution platform. This project will grow the capacity of current and future geoscientists to access, utilize, and collaborate within the growing ecosystem of open science resources, as well as contribute to advancing open science principles. We will propagate these principles through our workshops with recruitment specifically targeting under-served communities. We will contribute upstream to the open source stack upon which the Cookbook infrastructure rests. This project will catalyze significant new uptake of the NSF-funded Jetstream2 cloud computing platform. It will also provide intensive cross-disciplinary graduate training in climate science and open-source cyberinfrastructure, and enhance open science education experiences for numerous classes at undergraduate and graduate levels.

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1. Overview

1.1 Challenges and opportunities for data-driven geosciences

We are living through a revolution in Earth System science, in which the need for actionable information about our changing environment is ever growing while the size and complexity of the datasets are exploding, but while the ability of the working geoscientist to make effective use of the data to answer questions is not keeping pace. The complexity of Earth System problems demand collaboration across multiple large communities. The size and diversity of relevant observational and model datasets present substantial technical challenges to analysis, diverting attention away from conceptually important science questions. Moreover, technical barriers limit collaboration, as key datasets are often locked away behind authentication layers or clumsy access portals—and mechanisms to easily and effectively share algorithms and workflows are lacking. Ultimately, these challenges impede scientific progress and diminish our collective adaptive capacity and resilience. **There is a fundamental need for a more open approach to sharing both data and knowledge within the geosciences.**

The tools to address these Big Data challenges exist, yet substantial use barriers remain. Today's geoscientists require not only domain expertise but also high-level technical skills in an ever-changing computing environment. The scientific Python ecosystem has been a game-changer for many, providing an abundance of powerful and freely-available tools coupled to a vigorous open-source community. Recently, open-source communities like Pangeo [1] and Project Jupyter [2], working together, have developed effective frameworks for interactive data-intensive geoscientific analysis, and demonstrated successful approaches to moving scalable data-proximate analysis frameworks to the Cloud [3,4] – potentially enormous acceleration and democratization factors for geoscience [5]. For a relatively small community of technically adept users, these efforts have been extremely successful [6]. For less technically-savvy scientists, often trained on out-of-date workflows and legacy languages, the fast-moving tools and technologies in the Pangeo stack are often untapped, and can be a source of great frustration as well. Scientists spend an inordinate amount of time pondering questions such as: Which tool should I use? How do I use it? Can I trust it? Is it compatible with my existing data and workflow? Answers can be unclear or hard to find. The result is too much time spent navigating technology---or avoiding it---time that could have been spent productively doing science. **What's needed is a findable and trustworthy source of up-to-date tutorials for performant, scalable geoscientific analysis.**

There are inherent challenges in maintaining tutorials in today's rapidly evolving scientific computing world. Jupyter Notebooks [7] provide an elegant solution for assembling a *computational narrative* to tell a story with code, data, and rich text [8], making them an obvious choice for content delivery. Millions of public Jupyter Notebooks exist on GitHub, and they are increasingly used in STEM classrooms [9]. However, a recent study found that only about 4% of a large sample of GitHub-hosted notebooks were executable with reproducible results [10], either because the dependencies were not well described in the notebook and/or because upstream packages have changed, datasets moved, etc – what might be termed 'Jupyter notebook obsolescence'. Even curated collections such as the peer-reviewed NSF EarthCube Notebook Directory [11] suffer from this problem. *Effective workflow tutorials require more than a*

narrative that worked in some compute environment at some moment in time. We cannot address the significant knowledge gaps in our research communities with broken code; effective tutorials need to be executable in practice, not just in principle. **There is an urgent need for infrastructure that ensures health and reproducibility of Notebook content.** We will use the term “*Healing Notebook*” to denote content backed by such an execution and testing mechanism.

Automated testing allows for identification of failures, but fixing them and keeping Healing Notebooks healthy requires a community of people. One barrier is the duplication of effort across groups maintaining different tutorials on the same stack of Python packages. Can the geoscience community rally around a decentralized clearinghouse of Healing Notebooks that encourages collaboration and keeps good training material up to date? Such material needs to be *accessible* on two fronts: easily *findable* and *understandable* with context and required background knowledge clearly expressed. Meanwhile, best practices in the dynamic open-source ecosystem advance rapidly. How do people effectively share knowledge, collaborate, and link knowledge across sub-disciplines? Infrastructure plays a key role by enabling collaboration, findability, reproducibility, and reuse. But the success will ultimately depend on building inclusive communities of practice that incentivize individuals to make contributions to a shared resource. **We can reduce barriers to scientific progress by building community around shared scientific workflows.** That is the central goal of our proposal.

1.2 Pangeo and Project Pythia: progress in collaborative Open Geoscience

The above challenges are well known, and many efforts are underway to address them. Our team members are all active participants in Pangeo [1], a community promoting open, reproducible, and scalable “Big Data” geoscience [12]. Pangeo (funded in part by NSF EarthCube) is widely viewed as a success story in community-driven Open Science [6] and has made great progress in building both tools and social practices that break down barriers to collaboration and accelerate geoscience in the Cloud [5].

With the initial success of Pangeo came growing awareness of the knowledge divide holding back use of these transformative tools and practices across our research communities. Project Pythia [13] (hereafter “Pythia” – after the Oracle of Delphi of ancient Greek mythology) launched in 2020 with NSF EarthCube support to be the educational arm of Pangeo and serve as a community training resource for Python-based geoscientific computing. Pythia has a strong focus on the *Pangeo Stack* of packages (Xarray, Dask, and Jupyter). Pythia has two core goals: (1) reducing knowledge barriers by developing open, interactive, web-accessible learning resources built on public, cloud-hosted datasets that “just work” for users; and (2) growing an inclusive Open Science community around this content. These are well-aligned with recent proposals for building a successful “Open Source Science Stack” [6].

To date, Pythia has developed two primary educational resources: *Pythia Foundations*, and *Pythia Cookbooks* – housed on open GitHub repositories and served via our website. This content, along with the infrastructure and social practices that sustain it, are our first response to the challenges listed above.

Foundations is a geoscience-flavored introduction to the essential tools in the Scientific Python Ecosystem and Pangeo stack (e.g., JupyterLab, NumPy, Matplotlib, Pandas, Cartopy, Xarray, Dask), plus Python environment management tools (conda), basics of version control (git), and effective use of GitHub as an open source communication platform. In other words, it covers the foundational knowledge that’s needed to get started as a Pangeo citizen-practitioner. *Cookbooks* are crowd-sourced collections of advanced, domain-specific tutorials and exemplar workflows (or recipes) that build upon *Foundations* with explicit links to necessary background knowledge. The Pythia Cookbook Gallery (see screenshot) is our prototype solution for a well-ordered collection of accessible, reusable, and reproducible workflows.

Pythia content is built upon open infrastructure for *reproducibility* and *collaboration* that meets the Healing Notebook need. We believe this is a key distinguishing factor between Cookbooks and other content collections. Like many recent projects, we leverage Jupyter Book [14] to package notebook content as well-organized web pages. But we have built a cloud-based Cookbook publishing system on top of Jupyter Book that automates notebook execution in reproducible, curated computational environments. Users can interact with notebooks via Binder links [15], launching into an identical environment and reproducing the rendered web page content (e.g. graphs resulting from accessing data and running analysis code). The same environment is used for automated regular health-checking, which raises alerts about failed code and web links, allowing for a rapid healing cycle. Collaboration is achieved through GitHub Pull Requests that trigger the same execution infrastructure and a rich preview. *Cookbooks are collaborative, interactive Healing Notebooks.*

The Cookbook format is meant to incentivize community contributions of workflow knowledge: domain science experts drop their analysis code and narrative into an easy-to-use template, and quickly share a reproducible workflow – no hyper-specialized infrastructure knowledge required. Cookbooks are organized into a dynamic gallery with filters such as science domain and packages employed. In short, Cookbooks follow the FAIR principles for research software [16]: Findable via the searchable Cookbook Gallery (and soon, by DOIs); Accessible by anyone with a web browser; Interoperable through the

Pangeo software stack; and, to the best of our knowledge, uniquely suited to support Reusability thanks to our health-checking infrastructure.

Unidata, as part of its goal to support Python use, previously maintained its own tutorials. These were created both to support synchronous, in-person workshops as well as provide usage examples for libraries like MetPy and Siphon. With the advent of Pythia, Unidata has merged its content into Foundations chapters and otherwise aligned with Pythia's shared content. This has eased Unidata's ongoing maintenance effort and enriched user experiences with new features one-click Binder execution.

Since the Pythia website was first unveiled in 2021, its resources have been used by thousands to learn about modern methods for geoscience data analysis. Pythia has been used in university classrooms, it has supported numerous NSF and DOE sponsored workshops and hackathons, and it has attracted a growing community of content contributors. A principal focus of this proposal is accelerating and diversifying the community around Cookbooks. We are encouraged by a groundswell of interest evident in our recent outreach efforts and in the Letters of Collaboration appended to this proposal.

1.3 Our vision of a sustainable, inclusive open science community enabled by Cookbooks

“Cookbooks” imply collections of recipes for transforming raw ingredients (publicly available data) into scientifically useful results. We believe that a vibrant clearinghouse of well-organized, accessible, and inter-linked Cookbooks backed by a performant, portable infrastructure and an enthusiastic social culture of open knowledge-sharing will play an important role in moving geosciences fully into the cloud computing era. We outline below a number of specific proposals aimed at reducing barriers to knowledge, democratizing access to data, accelerating science, and nurturing an inclusive community. Cookbooks, seemingly just collections of notebooks, sit at the intersection of these themes.

Section 2 will describe planned Cookbooks addressing common workflows on high-value datasets. These will demonstrate geoscience advancement pathways in numerous domains spanned by our PI team and collaborators, and serve as seed content to attract broad participation in the Cookbook platform. A common theme will be accelerating science via Analysis-Ready, Cloud-Optimized (ARCO) datasets [4]. “Analysis-ready” describes data in a form amenable to expressive scientific investigation, e.g., quality-controlled aggregates along a time dimension that resulted from preprocessing large numbers of individual archival files. “Cloud-optimized” here refers to data formats that permit efficient, parallelized direct access to subsets of the data in cloud object storage. Initiatives such as Pangeo Forge [4] are working to reduce the significant barriers to producing open ARCO data from archival storage [3]. Pythia Cookbooks will help bring cloud-accelerated geosciences to masses, with accessible demonstrations of the enormous potential of cloud-based analysis, and pathways for new users to get started.

Achieving our vision will require targeted investments in computing infrastructure to mature the open-source stack that powers our Cookbooks and advance a performant, accessible, and portable cloud platform. It will also require investments in community-building. We will describe our plans for an annual workshop with specific recruitment and mentoring goals to grow the community while growing the content; the formation of a steering board to ensure responsive, inclusive, and sustainable growth; and synergistic alignments of Cookbooks with classroom education at undergraduate and graduate levels.

2. Accelerator science-driven Cookbook uses cases

We propose to develop science-driven exemplar Cookbooks that leverage specific *high-value datasets* spanning numerous geoscience domains and favoring scalable analysis of ARCO data, with content chosen specifically to accelerate community awareness and participation. The PI team, along with numerous community contributors (see letters of collaboration) have identified content foci spanning meteorology, oceanography, climate science, hydrology, glaciology, and applications of machine learning. These Cookbooks will seed substantial future growth through our community outreach and workshops.

2.1 Atmospheric Science: accelerating science with high-resolution reanalysis data

2.1.1 The ERA5 dataset: opportunities and challenges

Reanalysis datasets are central in atmospheric science: optimals blend of historical observations and state-of-the-art numerical weather prediction models [17], our best estimates of the continuous atmospheric state (e.g., winds, temperature, pressure, and moisture) over long time periods. The current gold standard is the ERA5 produced by the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF) [18]. ERA5 is distinguished from earlier products through its high-fidelity data assimilation, decades-long time span (1950-present), and very high resolution (hourly at 30 km horizontal spacing and 137 vertical levels). The full dataset measures roughly 5 petabytes.

Direct use of ERA5 data in meteorological workflows is challenging. The “raw” data capture state variables of the numerical model, such as spherical harmonics of vorticity and divergence of the wind field on terrain-following vertical coordinate levels. While these model-native fields are sometimes necessary for highly accurate time and space budgets, meteorological concepts are frequently better expressed in terms of standard variables on regular grids. Post-processed data are available on 37 isobaric levels, with some (often acceptable) loss of accuracy. The biggest barrier to scientific use is inefficiency of the underlying storage formats [4]: typically single variables and short time slices in legacy formats that do not scale well across the time dimension. ERA5 is thus a prime candidate for ARCO-formatting.

To meet this need, a team at Google Research has put some model-native ERA5 data into cloud-optimized stores in open GCS buckets [19]. Analysis-readiness in this context requires interpolated isobaric data; this is planned as follow-up work. We have identified two science use-cases for ERA5-driven Cookbooks. In the short term, our team will develop recipes for limited ARCO-formatted subsets of ERA5 sufficient for proof-of-concept (e.g., subsampling in time), and expand our Cookbooks as a more complete ARCO-ERA5 emerges.

2.1.2 Identification of Sudden Stratospheric Warming Events (SSWE) from ERA5 data

During boreal winters, dramatic breakdowns of the stratospheric cyclonic polar vortex occur at irregular intervals. Known as SSWEs, these events are known to influence tropospheric circulation patterns [20] and potentially drive mid-latitude cold air outbreaks. An example science question is, “Does the occurrence of a SSWE increase the likelihood of extreme winter weather in Albany, NY?” Such probabilistic questions are commonly addressed through composite averages taken over ensembles of discrete events. The typical workflow includes (1) obtaining data spanning a large number of years; (2) identify individual events based on an objective criterion; (3) aligning data on event dates; (4) clustering events based on some other criterion (e.g., did a cold-air outbreak occur?). Conceptually simple, clear methodology but vast data-processing needs – a great candidate for a Cookbook leveraging ARCO data.

We propose to develop an exemplar science-driven Cookbook that demonstrates a performant SSWE identification and compositing workflow on ARCO-ERA5. This effort will be led by Tyle in connection with his planned classroom deployments (section 5), and will be updated as best practices for performant ERA5 processing evolve. We expect this Cookbook to draw a lot of community attention, as it will perform a common operation on a high-value dataset.

2.1.3 Atmospheric energy transport and Arctic climate change

The Arctic is warming faster than the rest of the world [21], and this so-called Arctic Amplification (AA) of climate change is a near-universal feature of climate model projections of future warming [22]. While the phenomenon has been known for decades [23], the underlying mechanisms continue to be debated [24]. PI Rose’s group has recently pioneered a new approach to quantify the surface heating efficiency of winter-season surges of anomalously warm and moist air into the Arctic on scales of days to weeks – essentially the ratio of energy retained at the surface to the total energy source versus the energy lost through excess radiation to space [25–27]. This work clarifies a mechanism by which atmospheric circulation is contributing to AA both in recent reanalysis data [26] and in future projections [27]. It also illustrates how new climate science emerges from analysis of high-frequency weather data.

We propose to develop Cookbook content motivated by this research that demonstrates performant calculations of atmospheric energy transport from high-frequency reanalysis data. While the published research [25–27] leveraged NASA’s MERRA-2 reanalysis [28], there is evidence that the newer ERA5 has

advantages over MERRA-2 [29]. Thus there is scientific value in replicating the calculations [26] with ERA5, and the work will likely be publishable in the peer-reviewed literature as well as adding value to our ERA5 Cookbook efforts. PI Rose and students will lead this effort.

2.2 Radar meteorology: the Radar Cookbook

The Radar Cookbook was our first prototype and a significant driver of our existing Cookbook infrastructure. It currently focuses on basics of radar data analysis using Py-ART [30], and applications to science use-cases using a variety of data sources (e.g., NOAA NEXRAD network, ARM research radars). It is a collaboration between Pythia and domain experts at Argonne National Laboratory (Geospatial Computing, Innovations, and Sensing department) led by Dr. Scott Collis. We propose continued collaborative work on this impactful Cookbook (see Letter of Collaboration from Dr. Collis). The overall goal is to provide a deeper science focus while also covering tools and workflows. The next steps include (1) adding tutorial material comparing Py-ART against other specialized Python analysis packages such as wradlib [31] and xradar (a new open-source project to provide a common Xarray-based interface to various radar data formats), (2) deeper radar science training (e.g., dual-polarimetric fields), and (3) more in-depth tutorials on retrieval algorithms (e.g., dual-doppler). We will also coordinate with the Open Radar Science community efforts, including annual workshops at the European Weather Radar conference (ERAD) or the American Meteorological Society (AMS) radar conference. Dr. Collis's group will work with co-PI May and team to adapt content from recent ERAD courses into Cookbook format.

2.3 Climate science: cloud-based CMIP6 analysis

The Coupled Model Intercomparison Project, Phase 6 (CMIP6) [32] is the current state-of-the-art in modeling climate of Earth's past, present, and future. CMIP6 data volume was initially projected at 18 petabytes [33] but has grown far beyond. The version of record is provisioned via the Earth System Grid Federation in vast numbers of small, single-variable netCDF files. Recognizing the critical value of this dataset for climate research, the Pangeo community has rallied around efforts to port subsets of CMIP6 to ARCO-formatted open storage on various platforms. This has been a very successful effort in accelerating scientific use of CMIP6 – with the caveat that working in the cloud is still unfamiliar to large swaths of the research community. More and better-quality tutorials are needed to entrain colleagues into more efficient research workflows. The central importance of CMIP6 creates opportunities for high-impact Cookbook content that will attract a large audience.

Early examples of cloud-based CMIP6 analysis were housed in the Pangeo Gallery. Unfortunately that infrastructure has not been maintained, so Pythia has migrated content to a new CMIP6 Cookbook. Code has been adapted for recent changes in the stack, and new content on regridding for multi-model averages has been added, stemming from ongoing research in PI Rose's group. We propose to strengthen this Cookbook with additional common analysis workflows. PI Rose and students will lead this effort, drawing examples from our basic process-oriented research in climate sensitivity and feedbacks, pattern effects, and ocean-atmosphere coupling [34–43]. Our goal is to develop and maintain reproducible Cookbook content to accompany every published research paper. We hope in this way to model Open Science participation and explore new frontiers in scientific publishing.

2.4 Hydrology: the HyTEST project accelerated with Pangeo and Pythia

The Hydro-Terrestrial Earth System Testbed (HyTEST) project of the US Geological Survey (USGS) Water Mission is led by a team with expertise in hydrologic modeling, statistical evaluation, and data

science, including Co-PI Snyder. HyTEST provides workflows to researchers wanting to calibrate, evaluate, and test large-scale atmospheric and hydrologic models. The team facilitates community conversations to identify science questions and designs quantitative methods to test how well a modeling application addresses those questions. Questions include “*how well does the modeling application identify and simulate drought conditions,*” or, “*how well does the modeling application simulate streamflow in spring versus fall*”. These evaluation workflows leverage the Pangeo framework for scalable analysis and visualization of large model datasets. Published examples include [44–47]. Scientific papers supported by these evaluations include [48,49].

Co-PI Snyder will lead an effort to leverage Pythia content within USGS and deploy HyTEST’s domain-specific instructional materials as Pythia Cookbooks. This will not only avoid duplication of core material and make effective use of the reproducible Cookbook infrastructure, but will help promote these approaches in a larger audience of modelers working on similar problems. We hope this will also create community discourse around HyTEST’s model evaluation methods and their technical implementation, which may lead to further methodological and scientific improvements for model evaluation. Co-PI Snyder’s collaboration is an unfunded commitment from USGS supported by a Letter of Collaboration.

2.5 Glaciology: the Reference Elevation Model of Antarctica (REMA)

The vast Antarctic ice sheets hold the equivalent of 70 m of sea level rise. Precise quantification of their shape and size is needed as they face unprecedented rates of global change. Digital Elevation Models (DEMs) are raster representations of surface topography typically derived from satellite imagery [50]. For Antarctica, one of the highest resolution, continent-wide DEMs is REMA: the Reference Elevation Model of Antarctica [51]. A key feature of this dataset is the timestamping of individual grid points, allowing precise quantification of elevation changes over time. The full 2-m resolution dataset occupies 104 TB, demanding high-throughput ARCO analysis workflows.

Dr. Jonathan Kingslake (Lamont-Doherty Earth Observatory) developed early tutorial examples of cloud-based REMA analysis for the Pangeo Gallery using 8-m tiles stored as Cloud Optimized GeoTIFFs in a custom GCS bucket. As part of our migration of Pangeo Gallery content, we will work with Dr. Kingslake to develop a Cookbook using the cloud-native 2-m tiles now available in S3 buckets via the AWS Open Data Registry (see letter of Collaboration). A particular focus will be developing and documenting efficient workflows for lazy access of the entire dataset as an Xarray object rather than needing to query data catalogs *a priori* to identify the specific regional tiles of interest.

2.6 Physical Oceanography: sea surface altimetry and high-resolution simulations

The Pangeo Gallery contains numerous examples of cloud-based analysis of high-value oceanographic datasets originally authored by Dr. Ryan Abernathey (Columbia University). These include sea surface altimetry (a critically important satellite-observed signature of the dynamic ocean circulation) [52], and simulation products such as ECCO (Estimating the Circulation and Climate of the Ocean) – a state-of-the-art combination of observations and high-resolution ocean model [53]. The gallery notebooks focus on use of the Pangeo cloud and ARCO-formatted data for performant data reductions and visualizations – the kind of capability that allows for curiosity-driven focus on science questions.

The notebooks have suffered from obsolescence, and some datasets are subject to user-pay egress fees which limit their use as effective tutorials. We will work with Dr. Abernathey to migrate content to a more sustainable Cookbook maintenance regime (see Letter of Collaboration). Furthermore, we will pursue

Pangeo Forge recipes [4] to migrate key datasets to OpenStorageNetwork buckets to open up the tutorials to a much wider audience. Co-PI Eroglu will interface with Dr. Abernathey on this effort.

2.7 Machine Learning in the geosciences: The Pangeo ML project

The Pangeo ML project aims to develop high-level tools that serve a broad range of geoscientific machine learning (ML) applications. For example, the Kerchunk library enables Cloud-native access to archival file formats (e.g., netCDF3, HDF5, TIFF, and FITS) which are routinely created as part of scientific missions. CarbonPlan is developing a Kerchunk Cookbook (currently in final review for hosting on the Pythia Cookbook gallery) demonstrating how to use Kerchunk to enable remote, parallel access of NetCDF4/HDF5 and GRIB2 data. Led by Dr. Max Jones (see Letter of Collaboration), CarbonPlan will extend the Kerchunk cookbook for additional archival file formats (e.g., NetCDF3, FITS, GeoTIFF) and provide support for additional Cookbooks demonstrating scalable machine learning pipelines on large cloud-hosted datasets using open source libraries such as Xarray, Dask, Zarr, Satpy, Pyresample, Intake, and Xbatcher. Co-PIs Clyne and Eroglu will interface with CarbonPlan on this effort.

3. Infrastructure for Cookbooks and Open Science

3.1 Current state of our infrastructure

Cookbooks rest on an open infrastructure stack including Jupyter Notebooks, Jupyter Book, and BinderHub that enables us to deploy reproducible workflow narratives in a collaborative authoring and publishing system. We re-emphasize here the key importance of this infrastructure for delivering “Healing Notebooks” that solve the widespread obsolescence problem.

Our infrastructure is heavily reliant on GitHub for code hosting, collaborative development, and automation. GitHub encourages open collaboration through its “Pull Request” process, whereby any user can copy a public repository, make changes, and submit them for inclusion in the original repository. Pythia uses this process extensively for building and maintaining its content and infrastructure. GitHub’s focus on collaboration helps give users a sense of ownership and provides a path for others to get involved with the project at a deeper level – a key reason we teach its use in *Foundations*.

GitHub’s Actions service drives Pythia’s Cookbook automation. We define a publication workflow that takes unexecuted notebooks and configuration files and produces a rendered Cookbook, and reuse this workflow in a variety of contexts: as regularly scheduled “health checks”, and for submission and merging of Pull Requests. Any proposed change will re-trigger execution and automated publishing to a staging ground where reviewers can preview the direct web-rendered results. This allows for a collaborative review process and ensures correctness before changes are merged. Thereupon the updated notebook is automatically published to Pythia’s web portal; the web versions of these materials are automatically linked back to the source notebook, which become easily available to users.

While GitHub Actions provides some computing resources, most real-world scientific workflows have compute and data requirements that exceed GitHub’s freely available resources. A key component of our infrastructure is the ability to route notebook execution to other cloud platforms as part of the GitHub-mediated publishing workflow. We achieve this with BinderHub, another tool from the Jupyter Project providing notebook execution on demand within custom environments. We can direct each Cookbook to an appropriate BinderHub instance (say, one that is proximate to the necessary data) simply by setting a URL in a configuration file. The same BinderHub instance powers interactive user sessions, guaranteeing that users see an identical environment to the one in which the rendered pages were built. This is the technology that enables Healing Notebooks on Big Data.

3.2 Infrastructure needs to grow the project and the community

Our existing infrastructure has served as a proof-of-concept, but our vision of a cloud-centric Cookbook community requires new resources and expertise. Through this proposal, the Pythia team will launch a formal collaboration with the non-profit 2i2c. Co-PI Munroe represents a team with extensive experience managing supporting cloud infrastructure for interactive computing, and collaborating on open source development to facilitate open science. As a core value and policy, 2i2c contributes *upstream contributions* to communities where it is not the sole stakeholder, including the Jupyter ecosystem.

3.2.1 Cookbook-specific JupyterHub and BinderHub services

The Jupyter Project encompasses a robust ecosystem built around Notebooks. Viewing, editing, and execution typically occurs in web-based applications such as JupyterLab, which connects the notebook file to a runtime environment managed by a single-user Jupyter server. To support multiple users on shared infrastructure, JupyterHub is used as middleware to authenticate users and spawn separate Jupyter server instances. JupyterHub is often deployed with a shared computing environment among multiple users with unique persistent storage. JupyterHub can be deployed in the commercial cloud to provide a flexible and scalable data-proximate computing platform. Running computations in the same cloud region or provider can be an important consideration with very large datasets, both for performance reasons and to avoid network egress charges. Thus the ability to easily direct Cookbook execution to different cloud services is a key component of a broadly accessible learning resource.

We have already mentioned the importance of BinderHub to our Cookbook publishing pipeline. BinderHub is another Jupyter Project tool that powers the public “MyBinder” service [54], which enables researchers worldwide to replicate computational environments in the cloud. It can turn static code into interactive literate coding environments with a click of a button within seconds. BinderHub has also been deployed by many organizations for their own communities, including an experimental, low-powered Pythia BinderHub currently running on the NSF-funded Jetstream2 cloud environment. BinderHub works by *dynamically building* the software environment needed to reproduce a computation (using a tool called `repo2docker`), and serving this environment to users through a web browser. BinderHub was developed for use-cases that are *temporary* and *fully open* by design: sessions are unauthenticated and destroyed after a fixed amount of time with no persistent storage.

Pythia will require both BinderHub and JupyterHub deployments. While the public MyBinder provides some computation, each instance is relatively small. With NSF support, Pythia will have its own performant BinderHub (deployed and managed by 2i2c) to serve the health-checking and interactive use of Cookbooks. Environments will be cached between users giving a faster response time. This will give us the ability to spin up multiple Binder instances with control on the number of cloud resources used, meeting needs for larger simultaneous user groups such as at workshops. But most importantly, this will allow Pythia Cookbooks to use Dask, a Python package for distributed and parallelized workflows across arbitrary numbers of processes. Dask is a cornerstone of the efficient “Big Data” geoscientific workflows pioneered by Pangeo and essential for performant analysis of very large ARCO datasets such as cloud-stored CMIP6. Pythia needs a more powerful BinderHub to meet our project goals.

For Cookbook development, such as at our annual workshop, Pythia will also have access to one or more JupyterHub deployments. The key difference between BinderHub and JupyterHub is *persistence*, which is necessary during authoring and testing phases. This shared, persistent environment will be deployed with the common Pangeo Notebook Docker environment. To support the larger Pangeo

community, 2i2c will support the maintenance of these images to serve as standardized reference environments on which to build new Cookbooks.

2i2c prioritizes developing on infrastructure that is cloud-provider agnostic. With both JupyterHub and BinderHub, 2i2c has previous experience in deploying scalable, Kubernetes-backed deployments on any of the major commercial cloud providers. The decision on which provider (and which region) to use can often be decided based on data proximity. This has advantages to avoid vendor lock-in with any one particular provider. Casual consumers of Cookbook content on our interactive BinderHubs need not even be aware of the specific cloud service on which it's deployed.

3.2.2 Leveraging NSF-funded cyberinfrastructure to lower barriers to performant analysis

Dedicated funding for performant BinderHubs on commercial cloud services will allow Cookbooks to flourish as a teaching and learning resource. But what pathways might we offer to users who want to take exemplar workflows and scale them up to do new science? One answer is to leverage existing NSF investments in cloud infrastructure. Through the ACCESS program, individuals or research groups are able to obtain significant allocations on Jetstream2. We envision a seamless experience in which users clone a Cookbook and launch an identical compute environment under their own persistent allocation. This will be particularly beneficial for workflows that use fully open datasets with no egress fees, such as those on the OpenStorageNetwork. Pythia will help build this capability through our partnership with 2i2c, driving new uses of NSF cyberinfrastructure while broadening participation in open science.

Pythia has already obtained a Discover ACCESS allocation for Jetstream2 resources. Under this allocation (and more that we will likely seek if this project is selected for funding), we will begin to deploy highly scalable, Kubernetes-backed Pythia JupyterHub and BinderHub on Jetstream2. There are some technical challenges to be addressed. One key difference between Jetstream2 deployments (which runs the OpenStack platform) and commercial cloud providers is the lack of an 'auto-scaling' or dynamic node allocation feature. When deploying JupyterHub or BinderHub to Amazon, Google, or Microsoft's cloud, 2i2c is able to use vendor-supplied solutions that dynamically scale the number of nodes based on the demand. This keeps the deployment cost low while allowing for bursts of computing when there is increased demand. While OpenStack might have support for a similar feature through its Senlin clustering service, this does not appear yet to be a supported feature for Jetstream2. We have budgeted for anticipated development time to address these challenges, which *may* result in a significant broader impact in the form of enhanced Jetstream2 capabilities.

We specifically propose two different deployments, to be launched ASAP upon project funding: (1) JupyterHub and BinderHub on Google Cloud (budgeted in a separate CloudBank request) for use by Pythia Cookbook users and developers, with autoscaling available to keep costs manageable. (2) JupyterHub and BinderHub under a fixed allocation on Jetstream2. If Jetstream2 gains the additional functionality to enable an auto-scaling clustering service such as Senlin, 2i2c will prototype a dynamically scalable BinderHub deployment during years 2 or 3 of the funded project. These activities will be led, managed, and maintained by 2i2c with input from the existing Pythia infrastructure team.

3.2.3 The Cookbook as a scholarly object

Perhaps the final step in aligning Cookbooks with FAIR principles [16] is to assign them unique, persistent identifiers with citable attribution to content authors. This will not only make Cookbooks more findable but also incentivize scholarly contributions. There is a tension between the "frozen in time" archival nature of Digital Object Identifiers (DOI) and the rapid-cycle maintenance priority for Healing

Notebooks. DOIs are also oriented by design toward discrete digital objects such as code repositories, and there is some ambiguity around the citation of code versus the scientific narrative supported by the code.

We are inspired by parallel discussions across the open science community, such as AGU's "Notebook Now!" initiative [55] and the EarthCube Notebook Directory. We are in conversation with the Environmental Data Science Book community [56], who have developed a hybrid approach leveraging Zenodo-based DOIs for their source code repository and automated W3ID persistent identifiers for individual book chapters. The Pythia team will gather information about best practices and, prior to our first community hackathon, implement an automated solution to ensure Cookbook content authors receive citable attribution for their work with minimal configuration.

4. An annual hackathon in service of community-building

4.1 Overview and goals

Meeting our goals of building a vibrant and diverse Open Geoscience community around the creation, maintenance, and sharing of workflows will require bringing people together, and especially entraining people into the community who are not yet well represented within Pangeo. We believe that the best way to do this is to support in-person workshops or hackathons due to the open-ended brainstorming, networking, and unstructured relationship-building that is difficult to replicate in virtual formats. We have explicit goals to leverage our budgeted participant support costs to recruit from Minority Serving Institutions (MSIs) as one pathway to diversifying our community and broadening access.

We propose to host an annual summer event at NCAR tentatively titled "Pythia Cook-offs". The broad goal will be to **grow the collection of accessible, reusable, and reproducible geoscientific workflows in the Pythia Cookbooks, while broadening the community of user-contributors**. Specific goals: (1) create a forum for people to *bring their ideas, existing code, or rough notebooks* and collaborate on turning them into community Cookbooks; (2) bring together a critical mass of scientific content creators with infrastructure knowledge to identify and solve problem; (3) forge new collaborations with small-group project clusters; (4) propagate best practices through the community; (5) entrain a diverse group of new contributors with appropriate mentorship; (6) ensure each participant finishes the event with a persistent, citable contribution; (7) set the Pythia Cookbook initiative on a sustainable growth trajectory. The workshops will also serve as annual PI meetings for the funded project.

Our workshop design is informed by the HackWeek model [57]. We will collaborate with steering committee members for the successful *OceanHackWeek* (OHW) program (see Letter of Collaboration from Dr. Emilio Mayorga), which has been running annual events continuously since 2018. We will consult with Dr. Mayorga and the OHW team on best practices for participant recruitment, event organization, project cluster formation, mentorship, and post-event assessment. We expect that these conversations will occur a few times per year and lead to significant cross-pollination of ideas.

4.2 Workshop structure and outcomes

We anticipate 50-person at the NCAR Mesa Lab, leveraging its experienced support staff and well equipped facilities. Events will span four days. Day 1 will include structured tutorials, project pitches, group organization, and a structured social activity. Days 2 and 3 will largely be devoted to hacking on projects, with plenary check-ins and debriefs each morning and afternoon, and a mix of structured and unstructured social time. Day 4 will include presentations of group project outcomes.

Each event will grow the Cookbook collection significantly. Every Cookbook will be labeled with a persistent and citable DOI that credits all group participants. Small-group projects will encourage new

professional connections and spur future collaboration. Attendees will receive training in the Pangeo stack and Cookbook infrastructure, networking and oral presentation experience, and mentoring from experienced group leaders. All participants will make demonstrable contributions to a collaborative open science effort and discover how rewarding it can be to produce content for mutual community benefit. We will publish annual workshop reports in a peer-reviewed journal such as the Journal of Open-Source Education laying out the workshop goals, recruitment practices, accomplishments, and future plans.

4.3 Recruitment and funding support strategy

Meeting our workshop goals will require **recruiting a diverse group of attendees** with a variety of career levels, scientific backgrounds, and computing experience. Less-experienced participants will be intentionally paired with a group leader / mentor. We will advertise broadly through channels such as the Pythia website, Pythia Twitter feed, Pangeo Discourse and community meetings, departmental email lists, etc. We are collaborating with the NCAR office of Education, Engagement & Early-Career Development (EdEC) on a recruitment and retention strategy that specifically targets MSIs, leveraging EdEC's outreach network (see Letter of Collaboration from Dr. Curtis Walker). We will personally invite a small group of enthusiastic, experienced colleagues to serve as group leaders. As the cohort grows, we anticipate inviting past participants back as mentors in future years. A review committee will make selections for travel funding support with diversity strategies advised by EdEC. We will prioritize early-career participants with career interests aligned with Open Science, as well as funding cohorts of at least two participants per institution, particularly when recruiting from MSIs.

5. Catalyzing content development through classroom use

Continuing ongoing efforts by PI Rose and Senior Personnel Tyle, we propose to use several classes at the University at Albany (UAlbany) as test-beds for Pythia content and infrastructure. Rose has been a pioneer in the use of open-access Jupyter notebooks for interactive, reproducible lecture notes, including his well-known *Climate Laboratory* book [58]. Several courses taught by Rose and Tyle at UAlbany leverage the Pangeo stack for analysis and visualization and introduce computational reproducibility (inspired by [59]) as a backbone principle: *Climate Laboratory* (undergrad), *Climate Modeling* (grad), *General Circulation of the Atmosphere* [60] (grad), *Meteorological Data Analysis and Visualization* [61] (undergrad), and *Advanced Geophysical Data Analysis and Visualization* [62] (combined undergrad-grad); and beginning Fall 2023, also *Atmospheric Thermodynamics* (undergrad).

UAlbany courses will be delivered in Cookbook form and findable/reusable via the Pythia galleries. Students will use project-funded Binder and JupyterHub services for coursework. Pythia will benefit from an expanded user pool, organized user feedback, and predictable calendar cycles of demand for updates. Students will receive invaluable exposure to Open Science and specific training on contributing back to the community – e.g., packaging of data-driven term projects as Cookbook chapters and ingestion into the Pythia gallery via Pull Requests. We anticipate a positive feedback between class enrollment, community uptake, and advancement of project deliverables.

6. Project management and community governance

Pythia currently has working groups on infrastructure, education, and outreach. Regular virtual meetings are advertised on the Pythia website and open to the public. Working group membership is voluntary, and a rotating chair is appointed by PIs with leadership opportunities for junior colleagues. Pythia content is managed through GitHub Pull Requests and reviews by working group members.

For the next phase of Project Pythia, our goal is to separate PI-directed management of the funded project from the steering of a robust and sustainable community activity firmly situated within Pangeo. For long-term success, Pythia's content and infrastructure need to be responsive to the needs of the community and agile in the face of new innovations – a shift from 'for the community' to 'by the community'. Anticipating significant community growth, Pythia meetings should aim to be a forum for discussing issues and best practices for sharing workflow knowledge in the geosciences.

We propose the creation of a *Pangeo Education Steering Board* – a more formal, and broadly representative advisory council that can inform the priorities for Pythia's funded activities. In the first year of this project we will establish this board, with diverse representation across geoscience disciplines recruited and invited by the PIs, and including representation from MSIs (leveraging our workshop recruitment outreach efforts). Expected charges of this board include: guiding the establishment of a peer review process for future Cookbook contributions; identifying emerging best practices in educational efforts in computational geosciences; identifying potential duplication of efforts and inviting synergistic collaborations; advising on infrastructure priorities for the community.

These proposals are based partly upon Unidata's community governance, which is overseen by two committees with rotating membership. The Users Committee membership is staffed by community members familiar with Unidata's overall portfolio of products and services, and gives direct feedback on how this portfolio meets their needs. The Strategic Advisory Committee focuses on general strategies and opportunities at a higher level. Unidata's direct connection with its community has been crucial in helping the program be highly responsive to changing community needs over its 30+ year history. By creating a direct, community-driven advisory structure for Pythia, our aim is similar: to drive the project to be highly responsive and relevant to the on-going needs of the community.

This proposed work brings together a strong, multidisciplinary team of domain scientists and software engineers from academia, national centers, federal agencies, and nonprofits. Collectively we have deep experience with advancing geoscience and education, building open science communities, and the creation and maintenance of cyberinfrastructure for the geoscientific community. We are well poised to advance the project goals. Divisions of project tasks among the PIs and our collaborators are addressed elsewhere in this narrative, but briefly summarized here. PI Rose will oversee the overall project, supervise graduate students, collaborate with co-PI Tyle on the UAlbany-based content, research and educational initiatives, and liaise with other NSF-funded projects. Co-PI Clyne will oversee efforts at NCAR related to content development, outreach, and summer workshop planning. Co-PI Eroglu will manage on-going GitHub infrastructure maintenance. Co-PI May will oversee the Unidata efforts focusing on content development and maintenance. Co-PI Snyder will lead the hydrology Cookbook efforts at USGS. Co-PI Munroe will oversee infrastructure development and management work at 2i2c. The annual workshop will serve as a PIs meeting for strategic planning.

7. Project deliverables, success metrics, and timeline

Primary deliverables for this project include three hackathons focused on Cookbook development that will bring together a diverse group of geoscientists, software developers, and students. Tangible output of these events will be new Cookbooks hosted on the Pythia gallery with citable attribution to content authors, along with workshop reports produced by the PIs. The hackathons will strengthen the capacity of attendees to access, utilize, and collaborate with the ever-evolving ecosystem of open science resources, and will engender a growing community of practice around modern geoscience data analysis. Through our hackathons, community outreach efforts, and funded project participants, we will significantly expand the

collection of Cookbooks. We will deliver an open source infrastructure for supporting the collaborative authoring and maintenance of reproducible notebooks that is portable across commercial and NSF-funded cloud platforms.

Informative metrics are essential to the success of our project, both to help focus our efforts and assess progress toward milestones. Google Analytics, GitHub, and our BinderHub deployments provide a variety of useful data. We will track the number of entries in the Cookbook Gallery; numbers of chapters per Cookbook; numbers of individual contributors to our repositories; Cookbook usage metrics such as number Docker images spawned and consumption of cloud credits. Other metrics for our community growth include meeting attendance and numbers of applicants to our workshops. We will also track website visits to individual pages, and GitHub repo “forks” and “stars” to help identify popular (and unpopular) content. The user-contributor community is critical for long-term sustainability. Success of the project will be judged on growth of Cookbook content, use, and number of new contributors.

Timeline of major milestones (assuming a January 2024 start date)

	Year 1				Year 2				Year 3			
Milestones & Events	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4
Citable Cookbook infrastructure		◆										
Recruitment consulting	◆											
Recruiting		◆				◆				◆		
Hackathon			◆				◆				◆	
Advisory panel setup	◆											
Commercial cloud deployment	◆											
Jetstream2 deployment			◆									

8. Broader Impacts

Our project was conceived from the outset for broad impact. Cookbooks, one of our primary deliverables, will be freely accessible to anyone with a web browser, thus ensuring wide-scale usability by the most diverse spectrum of current and aspiring geoscientists regardless of affiliation, race, gender, or socioeconomic status. Moreover, the simplicity of executing – and even modifying – a complex exemplar workflow through BinderHub with the click of a button removes significant technical barriers that limit use of many open science computational resources to only the most technically savvy. Finally, the underlying thread of our Cookbook content is advancing open science: open software, open data sets, open computational resources, and open community practices. We endeavor to grow the capacity of current and future geoscientists to access, utilize, and collaborate within the growing ecosystem of open science resources, as well as contribute to advancing open science principles. We will propagate these principles through our workshops with recruitment specifically targeting under-served communities.

Our infrastructure development activities will result in upstream contributions to the open source stack. In particular, our infrastructure for collaborative authoring and publishing of FAIR notebooks is permissively licensed and in no way tied to the geosciences. We will look for opportunities to package our

infrastructure for broader reuse, potentially by upstreaming the technology into the Jupyter project. This will help maximize the existing investment NSF has made in funding numerous activities for which robust, informative, and FAIR Notebooks are a desired deliverable. Our development work and targeted use of JupyterLab for Cookbooks will catalyze significant new uptake of that NSF-funded resource.

The project will provide intensive cross-disciplinary training in climate science and open-source cyberinfrastructure for one or more doctoral students at UAlbany, and enhance open science education experiences for numerous classes of undergraduate and graduate students.

9. Results from prior NSF support

Rose: *CAREER: Understanding the role of oceans in the planetary energy budget* (AGS-1455071, \$544,681, 7/1/2015-6/30/2021). **Intellectual merit:** Fundamental understanding of how ocean heat uptake patterns shape climate feedbacks and sensitivity through modulation of atmospheric lapse rates, water vapor, clouds and circulation. Theoretical understanding of ocean-sea ice interactions in exotic climates including early Earth and high-obliquity exoplanets. Studies on the role of atmospheric transport on polar energy budgets. **Broader impacts:** Creation and maintenance of *climlab* software [63] and *The Climate Laboratory*, an open-access interactive textbook [58]; training of computationally-fluent graduate students: 3 MS and 2 PhD completed. **Publications:** 15 peer reviewed articles: [25,35,36,38–42,63–69]

Clyne: *Collaborative Research: EarthCube Data Capabilities: Project Pythia: A Community Learning Resource for Geoscientists* (NSF #2026899, \$690,689, 9/1/2020–8/31/2023). **Intellectual Merit:** The goal of this project is to provide a web-accessible, Jupyter Lab–based collection of training resources for learning to use the scientific Python ecosystem to analyze geoscience data, with a particular emphasis on developing scalable workflows and cloud readiness. **Broader Impacts:** Project Pythia is open-source, open-developed, and hosted on GitHub such that the resource can be used and improved by developers serving scientific domains beyond the geosciences, acknowledging that the difficulty learning the necessary technical skills in today’s modern Python ecosystem is a problem spanning many disciplines. **Publications and products:** No publications were produced under this award. Many products available via the Project Pythia website and the “ProjectPythia” GitHub organization.

May: *Elements: Scaling MetPy to Big Data Workflows in Meteorology and Climate Science* (NSF #2103682, \$598,024, 5/1/2021–4/30/2024). **Intellectual Merit:** The goal of this project is to address performance bottlenecks and improve the ability of MetPy to scale to large datasets used in a variety of meteorological and atmospheric science workflows, such as climate or ensemble modeling. **Broader Impacts:** MetPy is a freely available open source project that encourages community participation. The project has been cited or mentioned in 194 masters theses, dissertations, or peer reviewed publications. This award has also to-date supported 3 in-person or virtual training workshops focused on the use of MetPy. **Publications:** 1 peer reviewed article [70].

Eroglu: *Collaborative Research: EarthCube Capabilities: Raijin: Community Geoscience Analysis Tools for Unstructured Mesh Data* (NSF #2126458, \$879,946, 10/1/2021–9/30/2024). **Intellectual Merit:** Development of scalable tools that facilitate analysis on unstructured grid model outputs from global climate and weather simulations. **Broader Impacts:** A much needed analysis and visualization toolkit in an open-source and open-development approach where the broader community has a voice in every stage of the project lifecycle. **Publications and products:** No publications were produced under this award. Many products available via the Project Raijin website and public releases of “UXarray” package.

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